

Algorithmic Biases on X before the 2025 Polish Presidential Election

Tabia Tanzin Prama¹, Vishal Kalakonnar², and Przemyslaw A. Grabowicz^{2,3}

¹University of Vermont, USA

²University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA

³University College Dublin, Ireland

Abstract

This study examines whether the default algorithmic feed of X shows politically balanced content to users who follow presidential candidates and Polish political party members before the 2025 Polish presidential election. To address this question, we track news feeds of four sock-puppet accounts and analyze public posts of 485 Polish politicians and related users during the culminating month of Polish presidential election. We find that most of posts shown in the default algorithmic feed of X was from right-wing parties. The user most often appearing in the feed is the leader of the far-right party Konfederacja Korony Polskiej. We study the factors determining the appearance of a post in the feed of X, finding that the visibility of the extremes of the Polish political party spectrum is significantly amplified by the feed algorithm, possibly due to major platform updates following its ownership change in 2022.

1 Introduction

Social media have emerged as an important source of news. Half of adults say they at least sometimes get news from social media, according to a recent Pew Research study [1]. Politicians employ social media for election campaigning [2], while journalists use them in their coverage of political competitions [3]. Further, social media can influence people’s social perceptions [4, 5]. For example, about a quarter of adult social media users reported that they changed their views about a political or social issue because of something they saw on social media in the past year [6]. In particular, the social media platform X, formerly known as Twitter, is widely used for political activism by politicians and influencers, including the platform’s new owner, Elon Musk.

News feed algorithms determine the visibility of content on social media, yet they are typically opaque to the public, and their impartiality remains uncertain. In the case of X, users are given a choice of two news feeds, called For You and Following feeds, with the former being the default feed used by the majority of users. Both feeds rank content algorithmically. While the Following feed simply shows recent posts of users followed by the feed owner, the For You feed is driven by an uninterpretable algorithm that requires an algorithmic audit research to understand its effects. This study focuses on the algorithmic audit of the For You feed due to its prevalence and reduced interpretability.

One of the most important questions in social media research is whether news feed algorithms systematically amplify sensational, misleading, and polarizing content. A prior study, reporting on a massive randomized experiment conducted in 2016 on Twitter, did not find evidence that Twitter’s algorithmic feed amplify far-left and far-right political groups more than moderate ones [7]. That study, however, investigated an older version of the feed algorithm of X that was developed when the platform operated as a publicly-owned company under its previous name, Twitter. In contrast, a recent study of the political biases on X, conducted before the 2025 German federal election, suggests that the default

Political party	Accounts on X	Tweets	Endorsed candidate
Razem	30	5068	Adrian Zandberg
Nowa Lewica	29	2897	Magdalena Biejat
Bezpartyjni	8	872	Marek Woch
Polska 2050	27	1494	Szymon Hołownia
KO	156	30269	• Rafał Trzaskowski
PiS	144	34371	• Karol Nawrocki
Konfederacja	27	3455	Sławomir Mentzen
Korona	32	2507	Grzegorz Braun
None	32	9163	-

Table 1: The number of studied X users per Polish political party, the number of tweets they created between May 1 and June 1 2025, and the presidential candidate each party endorsed. Overall, we analyzed 485 users (listed in [Supplementary Information](#)), including 431 Polish parliamentarians and 49 other users who were among the top 100 most appearing in the For You feed, about half of whom represented a party account or supported a party. The names of the two presidential candidates who advanced to the second, deciding, round of the election, are marked with bullet points (•). The names of the remaining candidates are color-coded to mark the candidate they endorsed in the second round: Rafał Trzaskowski (blue), Karol Nawrocki (red), or neither (purple).

news feed algorithm of X amplifies extreme political content and shows more content of the far-right AfD than of any other German federal party [8]. Here, we build upon this study to test whether its conclusions hold also in the context of the 2025 Polish presidential election, and to shed light on the political neutrality of the main feed algorithm of X before a key election in Poland.

2 Dataset

To study the behavior of the feed algorithms of X before the 2025 Polish presidential election, we created two pairs of likewise sock-puppet X accounts that follow the same set of Polish politicians. Then, we tracked their feeds by opening the front page of each feed every half an hour, and saving a batch of 35 posts scheduled to be shown in the feed,¹ using an algorithmic audit tool [9].

The sock puppet accounts within each of the two pairs did not differ except for their assigned names and gender.² Each sock puppet of the first pair followed 11 presidential candidates on X (listed in [Supplementary Information](#)). By contrast, each sock puppet of the second pair followed 48 users in total: five members of each of the eight major Polish political parties, and the presidential candidates they endorsed. We order the eight studied Polish political parties from left-wing to right-wing: Razem, Nowa Lewica, Bezpartyjni Samorządowcy (Bezpartyjni), Polska 2050, Koalicja Obywatelska (KO), Prawo i Sprawiedliwość (PiS), Konfederacja, Konfederacja Korony Polskiej (Korona). The presidential candidate names that each party endorsed are listed in Table 1. Throughout the study, the four sock puppets did not engage with any content on X, except for following the specified accounts at the beginning of the experiment and then automatically opening their feeds.

To better understand the factors that determine post appearance in the For You feed, we additionally collected tweets of all Polish parliamentarians who have X accounts (431 politicians) and all politicians followed by the sock-puppet accounts. In addition, we collect posts of the 49 other users from the top 100 most appearing in the For You feed of our sock puppets, and identify among them the accounts affiliated with or endorsing one of the eight studied political parties. An overview of the studied

¹That said, only a few of these posts are actually shown on the front page when it is opened, since our sock puppets do not scroll.

²Their feeds were nearly the same. Our analysis combines information from the For You feeds of the four accounts by averaging the numbers of post appearances between them.

Figure 1: The fraction of the For You feed occurrences (red bars) and posts on X (yellow bars) of the 431 members of eight Polish political parties, ordered by their political ideology: from far left (Razem) to far right (Korona).

accounts per each party is in Table 1 and the full list of all studied accounts is in [Supplementary Information](#).

In this study, we analyze X posts published between May 1 noon and June 1 noon local time, 2025, a key period of the Polish presidential election, which includes the first round of the election on May 18 and the second round on June 1. For the purpose of this analysis, we filter out promoted tweets (ads).

3 Data analysis

We find that most of posts by politicians appearing in the For You feed are authored by members of the three most right-wing parties: PiS, Korona, and Konfederacja. The posts of far-right Korona accounted for 13.6% of feed appearances of politicians’ posts even though its members posted only 2.5% of all tweets authored by the Polish politicians during the study period (see Figure 1). We note, however, that this apparent boost in the number of feed appearances is similarly strong on the opposite side of political spectrum: the posts of the far-left party Razem constituted 15.1% of appearances of the political tweets in the feed, despite the fact that their politicians created only 5.1% of all tweets authored by the Polish politicians. These results suggest that X disproportionately highlights extremes of the Polish political spectrum, in particular the fringe parties: left-wing Razem and Nowa Lewica, center-left Bezpartyjni, and right-wing Korona and Konfederacja.

This analysis yields very different results for the two largest and influential Polish parties: KO and PiS. The posts of their members appeared less frequently in the For You feed during the study period than they tweeted. The posts of the politicians of KO, which leads the 2025 coalition government of Poland headed by Donald Tusk, appeared in the For You feed nearly four times less frequently than they were posted. That is, the KO posts constituted 10% of posts by politicians in the feed, despite amounting to 38.5% of posts tweeted by politicians. The posts of the politicians of PiS, which is the main opposition party that led the prior coalition governments of Poland between 2015-2023, appeared in the For You feed 17.9% of the time, even though they constituted 43.3% of tweets of politicians.

Most of posts in the For You feed are from users who are not followed by the feed owner. According to our measurements only about 20% of posts shown in the For You feed are from users followed by the feed owner, which is a significant reduction compared with the 50% reported by X in early

Figure 2: Fraction of users belonging to each of the studied Polish parties among the top 100 most appearing in our sock puppet feeds.

2023.³ This effect is due to the changes to the algorithm that happened after Elon Musk acquired the platform. For instance, a “major update” deployed and announced by Elon Musk in late 2023 aimed to “surface smaller accounts and posts outside of your friend-follows network”.⁴ However, there is no further information about these changes, so to our knowledge research community and broader public are not fully aware of their effects [10].

To account for the users who are not politicians, we identify the authors of posts whose messages appeared most frequently in the For You feed. The top five most-appearing users are presidential candidates: (1) Grzegorz Braun, the leader of far-right Korona, (2) Krzysztof Stanowski, an influential journalist who interviewed all presidential candidates, (3) Marek Kwoch, the leader of the independent party Bezpartyjni, (4) Karol Nawrocki, a Polish historian who won the 2025 election, endorsed by the main opposition party, PiS, as well as the president of the USA, Donald Trump, and (5) Adrian Zandberg, the co-founder and leader of the far-left party Razem. Among the top 100 users most appearing in the feeds of our sock puppets, 16% are affiliated with the right-wing PiS, 14% with the far-left Razem, 34% with the other six parties, and about 36%, including Krzysztof Stanowski, with none of the parties (Figure 2).

4 Feed algorithm audit

The differences in feed appearances across political parties may be due to complex reasons. Most importantly, the For You feed algorithm promotes more engaging posts,⁵ and the content of fringe parties may receive more engagements than the content of other parties, possibly because it evokes stronger feelings.

On the one hand, we find that posts of Konfederacja members receive on average more likes and replies than posts of other party members, whereas the posts of PiS members receive more retweets, and of Razem—more quote retweets (see Figure 3). These differences in user engagement partly explain the increased number of feed appearances of members of these three parties.

On the other hand, the posts of members of far-right Korona and left-wing Nowa Lewica attract fewer likes, retweets, and quote retweets than of the two major Polish parties—PiS and KO—and most other parties. Yet, the posts of Korona and Nowa Lewica members appear nearly as often in the feed of our sock puppets as the content of PiS, and more often than the content of KO. Thus, the differences

³A blog post by X claims that 50% of tweets in early 2023 For You feed are from followed accounts: https://blog.x.com/engineering/en_us/topics/open-source/2023/twitter-recommendation-algorithm.

⁴<https://x.com/elonmusk/status/1723021026752143705>

⁵<https://github.com/twitter/the-algorithm-ml/blob/main/projects/home/recap/README.md>

Figure 3: The number of likes, retweets, and quote tweets per average post published in May 2025 by the 431 Poland parliamentarians grouped by their political party.

in engagement counts among these parties do not explain how Korona and Nowa Lewica achieve this relatively large number of appearances in the feed.

Next, we investigate whether the For You feed algorithm favors content from the extremes of political party spectrum, while taking into account the differences in the numbers of engagements received by different posts. To test this hypothesis, we develop a model of the algorithm that regresses the number of feed appearances of each post of the studied users (politicians and the top 100 users) against four kinds of factors that might impact the appearances:

- five different engagement counts: likes, retweets, quotes, replies, and views,
- the ratio of the number of each engagement type to the number of views,
- whether the post author is followed, and
- whether the author is affiliated with one of the eight political parties or is unaffiliated.

We develop two types of regression models of feed appearances, shown in Table 2: (i) a Linear Model, which is less predictive, but more interpretable, and (ii) a more predictive Non-linear Model, specifically a gradient boosting regressor,⁶ which is more complex and harder to interpret. Both model types achieve relatively high accuracy: the Linear Model explains 24% ($R^2 = 0.24$) of the variance in the number of feed appearances, while the Non-linear Model explains 37% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.37$, computed on a held-out test set of posts).

According to these models, the two most important factors determining appearance of a post in the For You feed are the counts of likes and replies (see the largest regression coefficients of the Linear Model in Table 2).⁷ Additionally, both models consistently identify a significant relationship between the number of feed appearances of a post and the political affiliation of that post’s author. Posts authored by the politicians belonging to the extremes of Polish political party spectrum appeared in the feed significantly more often than we would expect based on the user engagements and other factors, both under the Linear and Non-linear Models of the feed algorithm. These results suggest

⁶<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.GradientBoostingRegressor.html>

⁷This analysis is much more complex for the Non-linear model, due to its limited interpretability. Our exploration based on an advanced explainability technique (SHAP) [11, 12] suggests qualitatively similar results as for the Linear Model, but we omit it for the sake of brevity.

Factor	Linear Model 1	Linear Model 2	Non-linear Model
Like Count	45.69 ***	45.15 ***	N/A
Retweet Count	5.19 **	4.16 ***	N/A
Reply Count	19.43 ***	18.87 ***	N/A
Quote Count	-1.66	-1.01	N/A
Views Count	10.10 ***	9.70 ***	N/A
Likes to Views Ratio	2.33	2.52 *	N/A
Retweets to Views Ratio	-0.10	-0.36	N/A
Replies to Views Ratio	-1.75	-2.11	N/A
Quotes to Views Ratio	-0.30	0.01	N/A
Followed by Feed Owner	0.24 ***	0.46 ***	N/A
Party = Razem	0.62 ***	-	0.61
Party = Nowa Lewica	0.76 ***	-	0.74
Party = Bezpartyjni	0.29 ***	-	0.28
Party = Polska 2050	0.45 ***	-	0.32
Party = KO	-0.15 ***	-	-0.16
Party = PiS	-0.017	-	-0.01
Party = Konfederacja	0.13 ***	-	0.19
Party = Korona	0.76 ***	-	0.74
Party = No Party Affiliation	-0.39 ***	-	-0.25
Number of Observations (N)	90 096	90 096	90 096
R^2	0.27	0.25	0.3694
Adjusted R^2	0.27	0.25	0.3693

Table 2: Results of the regression of the number of For You feed appearances of each tweet published by the studied users during the study period. For Linear Models, we show regression coefficients, whereas for Non-linear Model we provide the corresponding estimate of the extra feed appearance time gained due to party affiliation by the respective set of users (see Appendix A). Linear Model 1 and Non-linear Model analyze the impact of five types of engagement counts, their ratios to the number of views, whether the user is followed, and the political party affiliation of the user; Linear Model 2 examines the same factors but excludes political party affiliation. To compare the importance of different factors, we rescaled all of the factors so that they take values between 0 and 1. Both models consider all 90,096 tweets from 431 Polish politicians and the top 100 most frequently appearing users in the For You feed. As the target variable of the regression, we use an average of the number of appearances in the For You feeds of our four sock puppet accounts. The top 3 most important factors are in bold font. We indicate statistical significance at levels $p < 0.001$ (***), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.05$ (*).

that party affiliation is related to the For You feed appearances through factors other than the studied engagement measures, resulting in algorithmic boosting of visibility of the content produced by political extremes.

Far-right Korona, far-left Razem, and left-wing Nowa Lewica have benefited the most from this algorithmic boosting, according to our Linear and Non-linear Models of the For You feed algorithm: the regression coefficients for these parties are among the largest and statistically significant ($p < 0.001$, see Table 2). In contrast, the content of members and affiliates of the ruling party, KO, and their presidential candidate, Rafał Trzaskowski, was significantly down-ranked by the feed algorithm, resulting in a decay in the number of feed appearances: the respective regression coefficient is statistically significant and negative ($p < 0.001$). In comparison to these parties, the content of the main opposition party, PiS, and of the eventual president-elect endorsed by them, Karol Nawrocki, has not been boosted, nor down-ranked, by the feed algorithm: the respective regression coefficient is insignificant.

To better understand the impact of this algorithmic boosting, we estimate (i) a direct effect of the party-wise boosting on the number and duration of feed appearances per tweet per feed consumer and (ii) how much would the accuracy of our feed algorithm models deteriorate if they did not capture that

Figure 4: Estimated algorithmic amplification of appearances and exposure time in a feed of a post published by a politician of each of the studied parties. The boost in post exposure time (shown above bars) is computed by multiplying the respective party-wise effects on feed appearances by 30 minutes, since we measure feed appearances every half an hour. For PiS, the respective regression coefficient is not significantly different from zero. All other estimated effects are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The colors of bars encode the candidates endorsed by the respective parties in the second round of the election: Rafał Trzaskowski (blue), Karol Nawrocki (red), or neither (purple).

algorithmic boosting. To begin with, a party coefficient taking a value of one corresponds to an extra appearance of each tweet of that party in each relevant feed. Recall that we measure feed appearances at the beginning of a 30-minute time window, so one feed appearance can be perceived as the post being visible in the feed for 30 minutes, during which the feed was opened and the post was loaded into the client (and possibly shown to the user).⁸ Hence, if the regression coefficient for a party takes a value of 0.5, then this suggests *each* tweet of that party’s politicians gets an extra 15 minutes of exposure in each relevant feed.

Following this technique, we find that each post of Korona members, their affiliates, and their presidential candidate, appeared about 23 minutes more, and each post of Razem members and affiliates appeared 19 minutes more in the feed (see Figure 4). To estimate the total amount of extra exposure time that this algorithmic boosting may generate, the above extra feed appearance minutes shall be multiplied by the number of tweets produced by respective party representatives and the number of relevant feed consumers. Thus, the algorithmic boosting of political fringes has considerable effects. In fact, if we exclude the party affiliation variables from our models—thus neglecting to model the respective algorithmic boosting effects—the performance of the models drops considerably: from about 25% to 23% under the Linear Model (compare Models 1 and 2 in Table 2) and from 36% to 27% under the Non-linear Model. These results suggest that political party affiliations account for 2% to 9% of the variance in feed appearance counts.

5 Limitations

The accuracy of the feed algorithm models we developed, and the algorithmic boosting effect sizes we estimate using these models, are medium to large within behavioral sciences [13]. That said, there is an ample space for improvements. In theory, a perfect model, equivalent to the For You feed algorithm itself, could explain up to 100% of the mentioned variance in feed appearances. The development of a more accurate and realistic regression model would require access to the actual ever-changing For You feed algorithm and its input data, neither of which are available to independent researchers. The code of the early 2023 feed algorithm was released, but it is hardly helpful in interpreting and understanding

⁸For example, four appearances of a post correspond to the post being shown in a feed of respective users for about two hours, which is why our sock puppets would “notice” it four times during the four (possibly consecutive) measurements conducted every 30 minutes.

the algorithm’s behavior, since the release did not include sufficient information about its input data, nor model weights,⁹ and it was significantly altered *after* the release, as we note throughout this manuscript. Based on this information, we conclude that our regression models of the feed algorithm are limited in the following ways. First, the structure of our models is very different from the neural network architecture of the For You feed algorithm, which is composed of millions of model weights, considers thousands of factors, and is trained using a massive amount of user engagement data that only X has access to [14]. Second, there are factors that were not included in our regressions of feed appearances, such as the text and images of posts, the interests and characteristics of the feed owner, and trending topics. Some of these factors could be incorporated into future feed algorithm models. Third, the For You feed algorithm composes feeds in real time, as posts aggregate engagement counts, whereas our models are based on the final engagement counts. Algorithmic boosting of post visibility indirectly boosts also final engagements counts with that post, i.e., posts that appear more often in a feed will receive more user engagements. Hence, our results likely underestimate the effects of algorithmic boosting of political extremes, since in our analysis engagement counts are treated as if they were not boosted by the feed algorithm. The development of feed algorithm models that address this issue and capture the temporal aspects of feed composition necessitates access to a fine-grain temporal information about user engagements with a post, which is generally not accessible to academics.

6 Discussion and conclusions

The results of this study suggest that political extremes were amplified by the For You feed before the 2025 Polish presidential election. They tend to appear more often in the feed than one would expect based on the number of engagements (Section 4). Similar patterns were previously identified before the 2025 German federal election [8]. These results suggest that the over-representation of political extremes persists on X across countries, at least Poland and Germany, throughout the first half of 2025. However, a prior study of the 2016 feed algorithm of Twitter did not find evidence of amplification of political extremes in seven countries, including Germany [7]. We conclude that the feed algorithm of X must have changed considerably between 2016 and 2025. According to reports of independent researchers, the feed algorithm of the platform was significantly altered between 2023 and 2025, following Twitter’s re-branding to X and some of the changes favored the content of Elon Musk [15, 16], who acquired the platform in 2022.

Unfortunately, there was only one official code release of the feed algorithm, between March and April 2023. Major updates were announced soon after, in late 2023, by Twitter’s then new owner, Elon Musk, via a brief message on X, but their details, code, and explanations were not provided. Thus, the effects of these changes have been obscured and the public was not aware of them soon after the initial code release. Our study reveals, for instance, that the fraction of the For You feed outside of follower network was increased from 20% to 50% at the end of 2023 (Section 3). It is possible that the algorithmic amplification of political extremes was introduced at that time as well, e.g., as a side-effect of other meaningful changes. Given that feed algorithms may have a significant impact on civic discourse, political polarization, and stability of electoral processes, we believe it is important to periodically perform audits of key feed algorithms, particularly before major national elections, while extending their scope, as we discuss next.

We show that the majority of posts of politicians in the default feed of X are authored by right-wing politicians, and that the leader of far-right Korona often appears at the top of the feed. These results mimic the findings of the study conducted before the 2025 German federal election, showing that the party whose members most appear in the feed is the far-right AfD [8], actively supported by Elon Musk via repeated interactions and participation with AfD leader – Alice Weidel – in political events on X. While our algorithmic audit results suggest that more left-wing parties profit from algorithmic boosting than right-wing parties, it is probably more important that the algorithm down-ranks the content of the ruling party, KO, in comparison to the key opposition party, PiS, which endorsed Karol

⁹The code release: <https://github.com/twitter/the-algorithm-ml/blob/main/projects/home/recap/README.md>.

Nawrocki that narrowly won the election against the candidate of KO. Furthermore, this analysis does not account for a potential amplification of user engagements, described next.

Algorithmic disparities in exposures across party lines can translate into differences in user engagement and political support. Engagement counts are influenced by algorithmic boosting, as well as bots, possibly leading to the over-representation of certain partisan and demographic groups. For example, bots and right-leaning males were more likely to engage with election polls on X and Twitter, resulting in poll outcomes considerably biased towards Donald Trump before the 2024, 2020, and 2016 US presidential elections [17, 18, 19] and towards far-right AfD before the 2025 German federal election [8]. Similar patterns may exist for posts other than election polls. Furthermore, preliminary research suggests that coordinated bots engaged with the content of AfD before the 2025 German federal election [20]. While our study does not account for the impact of algorithms and bots on engagement counts and—in turn—on algorithmic boosting of respective content, future research shall fill this gap. Finally, a seminal prior work suggests social media posts attract more user engagements if they contain misleading information or conspiracy theories, due to their sensational or novel nature [21], potentially leading algorithms to promote such content more aggressively. This dynamic may incentivize content creators—including politicians—to post sensational or misleading material in an effort to maximize user engagement, thereby exacerbating the issue of political extreme amplification. As such, it is important to explore the relationship between feed appearances, bot activity, and misleading content in future research.

Biases in social media platforms—especially when presented as representative—can mislead users and shape public discourse and opinion in non-transparent, possibly even deceitful, ways. We need further independent social media research to keep our democratic societies informed. Such research requires access to relevant data from social media platforms (see Section 5). The European Union (EU), whose Poland and Germany are member states of, recently enacted the Digital Services Act (DSA), providing vetted researchers with a way to access data to study systemic risks to society from online platforms, including risks to public discourse and electoral processes in the EU. However, it is not clear whether platforms will fully comply. On the one hand, the US tech industry, accompanied by Donald Trump’s second administration, opposes such regulation [22, 23]. On the other hand, Donald Trump’s first administration, concerned about political neutrality of online platforms, drafted an executive order requiring online platforms to certify their political neutrality [24, 25]. We believe that achieving the laudable objective of political neutrality in online platforms requires that users are empowered to (i) switch between and (b) stay informed about platforms and algorithms. Platform transparency and accountability regulation, such as the DSA and PATA (bipartisan bill proposed in the US Congress [26]), aim to facilitate independent research and scrutiny of online platforms to inform users and policymakers. We call all stakeholders recognizing the importance of political neutrality of online platforms to support transparency solutions bringing us closer to this goal.

Acknowledgements

We thank the Naukowa i Akademicka Sieć Komputerowa (NASK) for creating the sock puppet accounts, sharing a list of X accounts of Polish politicians, and for their assistance in identifying party accounts and affiliates among X users.

References

- [1] L. W. a. N. Forman-Katz, “Many Americans find value in getting news on social media, but concerns about inaccuracy have risen,” *Pew Research Center*, Feb. 2024.
- [2] S. G.-F. Hughes, K. Allbright-Hannah, S. Goodstein, S. Grove, R. Zuckerberg, C. Sladden, and B. Bohnet, “Obama and the power of social media and technology,” *The European Business Review*, vol. 16, p. 21, 2010.

- [3] S. C. McGregor, “Social media as public opinion: How journalists use social media to represent public opinion,” *Journalism*, vol. 20, no. 8, pp. 1070–1086, 2019. Publisher: SAGE Publications Sage UK: London, England.
- [4] L. Muchnik, S. Aral, and S. J. Taylor, “Social influence bias: a randomized experiment.,” *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 341, pp. 647–51, Aug. 2013.
- [5] P. A. Grabowicz, F. Romero-Ferrero, T. Lins, F. Benevenuto, K. P. Gummadi, and G. G. de Polavieja, “Bayesian Social Influence in the Online Realm,” Dec. 2020. arXiv: 1512.00770.
- [6] A. Perrin, “23% of users in U.S. say social media led them to change views on an issue; some cite Black Lives Matter,” *Pew Research Center*, 2020.
- [7] F. Huszár, S. I. Ktena, C. OBrien, L. Belli, A. Schlaikjer, and M. Hardt, “Algorithmic amplification of politics on Twitter,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 119, no. 1, pp. 1–6, 2022. arXiv: 2110.11010.
- [8] T. T. Prama, C. Bagchi, V. Kalakonnar, P. Krauss, and P. A. Grabowicz, “Political biases on x before the 2025 german federal election,” *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2503.02888, 2025.
- [9] T. Piccardi, M. Saveski, C. Jia, J. Hancock, J. L. Tsai, and M. S. Bernstein, “Reranking social media feeds: A practical guide for field experiments,” *arXiv:2406.19571*, 2024.
- [10] B. Özturan, A. Quintana-Mathé, N. Grinberg, K. Ognyanova, and D. Lazer, “Declining information quality under new platform governance,” *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, July 2025.
- [11] A. Datta, S. Sen, and Y. Zick, “Algorithmic Transparency via Quantitative Input Influence: Theory and Experiments with Learning Systems,” in *2016 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, pp. 598–617, IEEE, May 2016.
- [12] S. M. Lundberg and S.-I. Lee, “A unified approach to interpreting model predictions,” in *Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.
- [13] J. Cohen, *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. New York: Routledge, 2 ed., May 2013.
- [14] J. Ferrando Huertas, “X’s Open Source Algorithm - Unveiling the code, but not the secrets,” *Shaped Blog*, 2023.
- [15] Z. Schiffer and C. Newton, “Yes, elon musk created a special system for showing you all his tweets first,” *The Verge*, vol. 27, p. 2023, 2023.
- [16] T. Graham and M. Andrejevic, “A computational analysis of potential algorithmic bias on platform X during the 2024 US election,” tech. rep., Queensland Univ. of Tech., 2024.
- [17] S. Scarano, V. Vasudevan, M. Samory, J. Yang, and P. A. Grabowicz, “Analyzing support for U.S. presidential candidates in social polls,” *JQD:DM*, 2024.
- [18] P. Grabowicz, “Using biased social polls from X to forecast the US election outcome? We see promise for this novel approach!,” *Uncommon Good Blog*, Nov. 2024.
- [19] S. Scarano, V. Vasudevan, M. Samory, K. Yang, J. Yang, and P. A. Grabowicz, “Election polls on social media: Prevalence, biases, and voter fraud beliefs,” in *ICWSM*, 2025.
- [20] K. Caunes and F. Lefebvre, “German elections: Digihumanism unveils massive pro-afd reverse censorship & bot-driven amplification on x,” *Digital Humanism*, 2025.
- [21] S. Vosoughi, D. Roy, and S. Aral, “The spread of true and false news online,” *Science*, vol. 359, pp. 1146–1151, 2018.
- [22] P. Blenkinsop, “We do not censor social media, eu says in response to meta,” *Reuters*, 2025. Accessed: 2025-04-13.

- [23] E. Gkritsi, “US Congress goes after EU over ‘foreign censorship’,” *Politico*, July 2025.
- [24] B. Fung, “White house proposal would have fcc and ftc police alleged social media censorship,” *CNN Business*, 2019.
- [25] D. McCabe and A. Swanson, “Us using trade deals to shield tech giants from foreign regulators,” *The New York Times*, 2019.
- [26] C. Coons, R. Portman, A. Klobuchar, and B. Cassidy, “Platform accountability and transparency act,” *Actions - S.1876 - 118th Congress (2023-2024)*, 2023.
- [27] P. A. Grabowicz, N. Perello, and A. Mishra, “Marrying Fairness and Explainability in Supervised Learning,” in *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, (New York, NY, USA), pp. 1905–1916, ACM, June 2022. arXiv: 2204.02947.

Appendix A: Impact of party affiliation in the Non-linear Model

For the Non-linear Model we estimate the effect of algorithmic boosting on the number of feed appearances as an average increase in the Non-Linear Model predictions of feed appearances, $\hat{y}(x, z)$, due to the activation of the one-hot-encoded party affiliation variable, z , that is,

$$\text{Boosting effect for party}(p) = \mathbb{E}_{i:z_i^p=1} [\hat{y}(x_i, z_i^p = 1) - \hat{y}(x_i, z_i^p = 0)],$$

where party affiliation of the author of post i is encoded with binary variables z_i^p , while x_i corresponds to all other (non-party) factors characterizing post i , such as engagement counts and ratios, and the average is over the set of posts i authored by users affiliated with party p . Note that this measure of the effect on algorithmic boosting on the number of feed appearances is consistent across the Linear and Non-linear Models. That is, if the above formula is applied to the Linear Model, it will return its respective regression coefficients, and the respective results for the two models are comparable, which is why we include both model types in Table 2. The above measure has previously been introduced in a general context as *marginal direct effect* (MDE [27]). It captures the direct impact of given input factor on model output. In reality, however, this effect may correspond to indirect impact through other factors that are *not* included in our models of the feed algorithm.